

Links and Blocks: the Role of Language in Samuel Beckett's Selected Plays

Authors : Su-Lien Liao

Abstract : This article explores the language in the four plays of Samuel Beckett-*Waiting for Godot*, *Endgame*, *Krapp's Last Tape*, and *Footfalls*. It considers the way in which Beckett uses language, especially through fragmentation utterances, repetitions, monologues, contradictions, and silence. It discusses the function of language in modern society, in the theater of the absurd, and in the plays. Paradoxically enough, his plays attempts to communicate the incommunicability of language.

Keywords : language, Samuel Beckett, theater of the absurd, foreign language teaching

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